

Stepwise Stability Constants of Copper-2-Hydroxy Methyl Benzimidazole in 50% Ethanol

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THE determination of stability constants by e.m.f. measurements of metal in equilibrium with complexes of metal was first attempted by Riley and Gallafent¹. In the present investigation, Leden method was employed to determine the stepwise stability constants of Cu-2-HMBMA complex in 50% ethanol.

Experimental and Results

The following two cells were set up

Cell-A	SCE	KNO ₃ salt bridge	2 ml 0.01 M CuSO ₄	+	Cu
			+2 ml 1.0 M KNO ₃		
			+4 ml EtOH		
			+12 ml 50% EtOH		
Cell-B	SCE	KNO ₃ salt bridge	2 ml 0.01 M CuSO ₄	+	Cu
			+2 ml 1.0 M KNO ₃		
			+4 ml EtOH		
			+x ml 0.1 M HMBMA in 50% EtOH		
			+y ml 50% EtOH		
			(x+y=12 ml)		

The potentiometric measurements were carried out at 35±1° using Leeds and Northrup potentiometer having accuracy of ±0.1 mV. Copper electrode was prepared² and its reversibility was checked from time to time during the measurements. The results are given in Table-1.

TABLE-1

Sr. No.	'X'	'Y'	E ₂ Volts	ΔE (E ₁ -E ₂)	(L) X 10 ³
1	0.0	12.0	+0.0485(E ₁)	-	-
2	1.0	11.0	-0.1157	0.1642	1
3	2.0	10.0	-0.1735	0.2220	6
4	3.0	9.0	-0.1809	0.2294	11
5	4.0	8.0	-0.2132	0.2617	16
6	5.0	7.0	-0.2281	0.2766	21
7	6.0	6.0	-0.2403	0.2888	26
8	7.0	5.0	-0.2485	0.2970	31
9	8.0	4.0	-0.2534	0.3019	36
10	9.0	3.0	-0.2724	0.3209	41

The e.m.f. of Cell-B is given by

$$E_2 = E' + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln (M)$$

where (M) is the free metal ion concentration. In the above equation E' includes the potential of the calomel electrode, the liquid junction potential and

the correction term for activity coefficient in the mixed solvent. In the case of Cell-A, when no ligand is added the e.m.f. of the cell is given by

$$E_1 = E' + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln (C_M)$$

where (C_M) is the metal ion concentration. When ligand is added some of the metal ions are removed to form a complex and new potential, E₂ will be set up. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E = E_1 - E_2 &= \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left(\frac{C_M}{M} \right) \\ &= \frac{0.06105}{n} \log \left(\frac{C_M}{M} \right) \text{ at } 35^\circ \end{aligned}$$

The quantity (C_M/M) is known as the degree of formation and is designated as φ, so that,

$$\log \phi = \frac{nF}{2.303RT} \cdot \Delta E$$

According to Leden³,

$$F_n(L) = \frac{F_{n-1}(L) - \beta_{n-1}}{(L)} = \beta_n$$

From the above equation it is easy to calculate F_n(L)

TABLE-2

Sr. No.	(C _M /M)	F ₁ (L)	F ₂ (L)	F ₃ (L) × 10 ⁻¹⁴	F ₄ (L) × 10 ⁻¹⁵
1	-	-	-	-	-
2	2.410 × 10 ⁸	2.411 × 10 ⁸	7.500 × 10 ¹⁰	0.147	2.730
3	1.905 × 10 ⁷	3.174 × 10 ⁹	5.012 × 10 ¹¹	0.735	10.240
4	2.856 × 10 ⁷	2.597 × 10 ⁹	2.234 × 10 ¹¹	0.148	0.256
5	3.784 × 10 ⁸	2.365 × 10 ¹⁰	1.468 × 10 ¹²	0.880	4.750
6	1.169 × 10 ⁹	5.541 × 10 ¹⁰	2.630 × 10 ¹²	1.224	5.251
7	2.951 × 10 ⁹	1.134 × 10 ¹¹	4.361 × 10 ¹²	1.654	5.899
8	5.470 × 10 ⁹	1.764 × 10 ¹¹	5.790 × 10 ¹²	1.848	5.573
9	7.943 × 10 ⁹	2.206 × 10 ¹¹	6.127 × 10 ¹²	1.684	4.344
10	3.311 × 10 ¹⁰	8.075 × 10 ¹¹	1.970 × 10 ¹³	4.790	11.390

* Serial numbers correspond to those given in Table 1

Discussion

If F₁(L) is plotted versus (L), the intercept will be β₁ and slope will be β₂. Similarly if F₂(L) is plotted versus (L), limiting slope will be β₃ and intercept will be β₂. Hawkins and Perrin⁴ have reported stability constants of copper benzimidazole. The values of log K₁, log β₂, log β₃ and log β₄ at ionic strength of 0.15 M NaClO₄ were 3.56, 6.34, 9.0, 10.91. The values of log K₁ and log K₂ were 3.56 and 2.78. In the present case, log K₁ and log K₂ of copper-2-HMBMA are 8.22 and 2.56. The lower value of log K₂ for Cu-2-HMBMA complex may be due to the steric effect of 2-substituent. From the

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figure the stepwise stability constants will be as given below ;

Complex	Log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃	log K ₄
Cu(HMBMA) ₄ SO ₄	8.22	2.56	2.30	2.70
			log β ₄ = 15.78	

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References

- H. L. Riley and V. Gallafent, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2029.
- S. K. Patel, Ph.D. thesis Gujarat University, 1969 p. 126.
- I. Leden, *Z. Physikal Chem.*, 1941, A188, 160, vide A. G. Desai and M. B. Kabadi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 805.
- C. J. Hawkins and D. D. Perrin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 351.

Nickel (II) Complexes of some new Tridentate (ONN) Dibasic Schiff Bases

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ALTHOUGH transition metal complexes of salicyldehyde schiff bases have been extensively studied^{1,2}, very little work has been reported³ particularly on the coordination behaviour of ONN

donor tridentate schiff bases (derived from salicyldehyde). This preliminary communication reports syntheses and characterisation of several nickel(II) complexes with four new schiff bases derived from salicyldehyde or 5-substituted salicyldehyde and nitroaminoguanidine.

Experimental

(A) *Syntheses of schiff bases :*

All the four schiff bases were prepared by refluxing a mixture of aqueous alcoholic solutions of nitroaminoguanidine (0.01 mole) and R-salicyldehyde (0.01 mole) (R=H, 5-Cl, 5-Br and 5-NO₂) for one hour. The schiff bases (R-SBH₂) having light yellow colour with varying shades, are insoluble in water but soluble in aqueous alcohol (R=5-Cl, 5-Br) or in alkaline alcoholic solution (R=H, 5-NO₂) Anal : R-SBH₂ :

- R=H m.p. 220° (d), (Found : N, 31.80 ; C, 42.84 ; H, 3.82. Calcd for C₈H₉O₈N₂ : N, 31.45 ; C, 43.05 ; H, 4.03%)
- R=5-Cl m.p. 225° (d), (Found : N, 27.52 ; C, 37.42 ; H, 2.90. Calcd for C₈H₈O₈N₂Cl : N, 27.18 ; C, 37.28 ; H, 3.10%)
- R=5-Br m.p. 227° (d), (Found : N, 22.98 ; C, 31.52 ; H, 2.44. Calcd for C₈H₈O₈N₂Br : N, 23.18 ; C, 31.79 ; H, 2.65%)
- R=5-NO₂ m.p. 252° (d), (Found : N, 31.68 ; C, 35.60 ; H, 2.72. Calcd for C₈H₈O₈N₄ : N, 31.34 ; C, 35.83 ; H, 2.98%)

(B) *General method for the syntheses of the complexes :*

- [NiR-SB H₂O]_n H₂O (R=H, 5-Cl, 5-Br, 5-NO₂)

On mixing either an alcoholic solution (R=5-Cl, 5-Br) or an alkaline alcoholic solution (R=H, 5-NO₂) of the schiff base (0.01 mole) with an aqueous alcoholic solution of NiCl₂ · 6H₂O (0.01 mole), a deep red solution resulted, when the pH of the solution was adjusted to 6~7 by addition of dil NaOH or ammonia solution whenever necessary. The resulting solution was refluxed for one hour and the orange-red compound, in each case, was collected on the filter, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over silica gel.

- [NiR-SBX]_nH₂O (X=py, β-picoline and γ-picoline)

These mixed ligand complexes were prepared either by reaction of the corresponding aquo-variety (suspended in alcohol) with the respective base and subsequent evaporation of the resulting solution on water bath or by refluxing a mixture of schiff base (0.01 mole), NiCl₂ · 6H₂O (0.01 mole) and the corresponding base (0.01 mole) in aqueous alcoholic or alkaline ethanolic solution. In each case, an orange-yellow compound was collected, dried as before by washing with alcohol and acetone.